

mobiOS

Improving waste management of biobased plastics and the upcycling in packaging, textile, and agriculture sectors

MoeBIOS is an application of the circular (bio)economy concept: the development of three value chains incorporating separate recycling streams for bioplastics (BP's) to improve waste management efficiency throughout Europe. It is a systemic innovation: it will create linkages addressed at the different key stages of the whole chains to solve a hierarchical challenge, from the collection of the bioplastic waste (simulated streams), up to the upcycling and validation of the final recycled end-products (holistic and coordinated solution).

Project Duration:

48 month. *June 2024 - May 2028*

9,7
M€

Total Cost

7
M€

EU Contribution

Areas:

Food, Bioeconomy,
Natural Resources,
Agriculture
and Environment

The new value chain will imply sorting, conditioning and valorising three types of waste streams from the packaging, agriculture and textile industries into three end-products, targeting to reach at least the same quality and functionality than the original grades, while the end users' acceptance will be assessed as well. As cornerstone targets for maximizing project's impact, the upscaling of the recycling processes will:

Coordinated by
ITENE,
Instituto tecnológico
del Embalaje,
Transporte y Logística

21 partners.
Spain, France, Italy,
Germany, Netherlands,
Slovakia

1 Be integrated in pilot plants on the premises of actual industrial recycling lines currently operating in waste management companies, not disrupting them, and reaching a final TRL = 6/7 or even beyond.

2 Focus on bioplastics for which recycling processes are still not in place, excluding bio-based analogues ("drop-ins"): PLA and PLA blends, PHA and its blends, PBS and PEF, accordingly with the market. The use of PBAT will be assessed as well.

A Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) and a transdisciplinary methodology will engage waste producers, waste managers, bio-based and (bio)plastics industry, public authorities, standardization agencies, citizens and media multipliers, creating a co-creation and co-ownership innovation environment of + 50 participants.

Work packages

WP1 **Turning waste point into opportunities**

WP2 **Novel technologies for enhancing biobased plastics waste recycling**

WP3 **Development of demonstrators base on recycled biobased plastics**

WP4 **Integration of the circular value chain**

WP5 **Sustainability, safety and techno-economy assement**

WP6 **Communication, dissemination, exploitation and SSH**

WP7 **Project Management**

How the challenge is addressed:

moeBIOS

MoeBIOS project coordinator:

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**Funded by
the European Union**

**Circular
Bio-based
Europe**
Joint Undertaking

**Bio-based Industries
Consortium**

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